

Analysis Of The Evolving Cultural Tourism Implementation In Bali Indonesia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 17, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 27, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Tri Hita Karana, Cultural Tourism, Balinese Culture, Bali Cultural Tourism Development Model</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5035637</p>	<p><i>This article presents Bali cultural tourism implementation analysis, a qualitative research analysing data gathered through observation, document, and interviews with stakeholders. Results showed tourism contributes significantly to Bali economy; however, it has not maintained the sustainability of Balinese community, culture and nature, caused by implementation inconsistency, low enforcement, and lack stakeholder understanding. Academics are occupied by foreign-based tourism discourses, which could actually come under Bali cultural tourism flag. Local regulations on the issue do not have power to oversee the development. It is expected, the analysis and the development model formulated could become a reference for tourism stakeholders in Bali.</i></p>

Introduction

Tourism stakeholders define cultural tourism differently due to the different emphasis applied to the concept. Cultural tourism defined broadly as “a type of tourism activity in which the visitor’s essential motivation is to learn, discover, experience and consume the tangible and intangible cultural attractions/products in a tourism destination (UNWTO - General Assembly, 2017). Whilst, Oelkers (2007) discussed the construct in a more detail manner; precisely, cultural tourism that concentrates on the culture of the region as attractions, inclusive of heritage, art, food, clothing, geographic points of interest, historic sites and museums. The Organisation of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (2009) defines culture in relation to tourism, as something that attracts tourists and which differentiates destinations from one another. It is a source of identity and differentiation in the face of globalisation.

Culture itself is a complex construct that is a challenge to define. Hundreds of experts from all over the world have tried to define it without any definite agreement. Nonetheless, this concept is relatively easier to understand when being viewed from the universal element of culture as defined by a famous Indonesian anthropologist Koentjaraningrat. According to Koentjaraningrat (2000), these elements include religion, society, knowledge, language, art, livelihoods, and tools.

Cultural tourism is supportive to the community's economy and preserve the culture itself (Richards, 2001) but in practice, cultural tourism is a challenge to conceptualise, especially because of the unique nature of culture at different corner of the world. There are particularly significant differences between the objects or attractions of cultural tourism in the West and in the East or between modern and traditional community. In Western countries, cultural tourism offers types of products such as museums, heritage, and modern events. In Eastern countries, cultural tourism relies on its rich traditions, arts and culture. Related to this, Fagence (2003) notes there are three groups of cultural tourism. (1) Highly institutionalized culture - including museums, exhibitions, visual art, historic sites, theaters, performing arts, and literature, science and technology centers; (2) Popular folk culture - including film, entertainment, sport, mass media, shopping, events, food, produce, crafts, customs, and traditions; (3) Symbolic ethnic culture - including folkways, vernacular architecture, education, transport, religion, dress, language and work patterns. Based on the view of Fagence (2003), cultural tourism in Western countries includes highly institutionalized culture and most of the elements are popular folk culture. The cultural tourism in Eastern countries, including in the tourist destination of Bali which is the location of this research, mostly covers the elements of symbolic ethnic culture and partially a part of popular folk culture.

Bali Province is an international tourist destination which is very popular not only in Indonesia but also regionally (Asia) and internationally. Prior to the emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic since early 2020, foreign tourist visits in Bali in the last five years were thriving: 4,001,835 (2015), 4,927,937 (2016), 5,697,739 (2017), 6,070,473 (2018), 6,275,210 (2019) (Badan Pusat Statistik - Statistics of Bali Province, 2020). These figures exceed the number of tourist visits at all other tourist destinations in Indonesia, which shows the success of the tourism industry in Bali. Even in early 2021, amid the continuing period of Covid-19 pandemic, the world's largest travel platforms 'Tripadvisor', placed Bali on top of its 2021 list of World's Most Popular Destinations, with London and Dubai being the second and third ranks (Daniels, 2021).

The uniqueness of Bali tourism development lies in the choice of paradigm adopted for the development. Bali tourism development legally and formally adopts the paradigm of cultural tourism, in which, Bali Regional Regulation Number 3 of 1974 concerning Cultural Tourism was issued. Because it was a new and innovative idea, this regional regulation is an example in Indonesia and a capital for Bali's tourism development in the future (Anom, et al, 2017). This regulation was later revised to become Bali Regional Regulation No.3 of 1991 concerning Cultural Tourism. Finally, Bali Regional Regulation Number 2 of 2012 concerning Bali Cultural Tourism was released and has been in effect until now, which revises the previous regional regulation.

Bali Provincial Regulation Number 2 of 2012 concerning Bali Cultural Tourism, Chapter I Article 1 Paragraph 14 states "Bali Cultural Tourism is Bali tourism which is based on Balinese Culture that is rooted from the teachings of Hinduism and the Tri Hita Karana as the main philosophy capital using tourism as a vehicle for actualization, so as to create a dynamic and reciprocal relationship between tourism and culture which makes them develop synergistically, harmoniously and sustainably in order to provide prosperity to the community, as well as the preservation of cultural and environmental".

In the life of Balinese people, Hinduism, Balinese culture, and Tri Hita Karana philosophy are conceptually inseparable from one another (Figure 2). The Balinese Hindu community practices the Tri Hita Karana (Windia and Dewi, 2007; Mudana, 2018), which is the harmony of relationships between God, humans and the physical environment. Hinduism as the root of Balinese culture has also been explained by scholars such as Picard (1996) and Mantra (1992; 1996). In other words, Balinese culture is Hinduism with its Tri Hita Karana. From this perspective, it is appropriate that cultural tourism be used as a paradigm and even become the identity of Bali tourism development. However, the implementation of Bali cultural tourism has not been maximal, the irony is that there are ample tourism projects forgo the principle; the existence of Balinese culture, the nature and the sustainability of the Balinese people need to be synergized with the progress of tourism (economy) so that the development of cultural tourism in Bali can be successful as expected together.

Some researches on cultural tourism in Bali have been carried out by a number of researchers, but as far as the author is aware, none has discussed specifically about the development and evolution of its implementation. The works of Picard (1995; 1996; 1997), who have been known as an expert in Bali cultural tourism, have never discussed the issue of the implementation of cultural tourism in question. Ardika (2003) who researched sustainable cultural tourism in Bali and Anom et al (2017) who wrote the hundred-year stages of Bali tourism also did not touch on this. For this reason, this paper aims to identify the problem of not maximizing the implementation of Bali cultural tourism, especially what happened before the Covid-19 pandemic and how solutions are offered for improvement.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research data were mainly obtained from document studies. Apart from the Bali Regional Regulation Number 2 of 2012 concerning Bali Cultural Tourism and other related government regulations; the author also reviews relevant and scientific publications such as: journal articles, books, and other materials, both printed and online. This data collection activity was carried out in the middle to the end of 2020 to the publications containing tourism activities in Bali when the number of tourist visits to Bali reached one of its peak points during the years before the negative impact of Covid-19 pandemic on Bali tourism. In some parts, these techniques are complemented by observation and interviews as a triangulation for the sake of completing the data obtained (Stokes, 2006). Interviews were conducted among others with the Chairman of the Association of Indonesian Hotels and Restaurants in Bali who is also Deputy Governor of Bali Cokorda Oka Artha Ardhana Sukawati and several tourism practitioners and figures as well as community members.

The data analysis used is qualitative data analysis, namely the data compaction method by developing a taxonomy, descriptive classification system or chronological classification which includes the amount of information collected and demonstrates its systematic association (Wuisman, 1996: 300). The steps in the analysis technique are in accordance with the recommendations of Miles and Huberman (1992: 15-19), namely data reduction, data presentation, and drawing the inferences and conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The phenomenon of cultural tourism in Bali as a tourism development type that has a particular identity is interesting to discuss considering that tourism that is widely developed in the world is generic tourism such as natural tourism, artificial tourism, shopping tourism, and others. The uniqueness of Bali cultural tourism lies in the prominence of Balinese cultural identity with its Hindu and Tri Hita Karana characters which are supported by its physical geographic position as a separate archipelago in Indonesia.

Cultural tourism in Bali since its inception in 1974 until now can generally be said to have been able to support the development of Bali tourism so far, but in some way it cannot be denied that many elements of cultural tourism itself must be improved and perfected. Even a number of studies such as Suetha (1999) and Mudana (1999) have concluded that cultural tourism is not implemented as it should. Bagus (2004: 270) states that Bali tourism is capitalistic, which means that this business has not provided welfare justice for the community. The Deputy Governor of Bali and also the General Chair of the Bali Hotel and Restaurant Association Cokorda Oka Artha Ardhana Sukawati honestly admitted that even though it is based on cultural tourism, Bali tourism has not provided welfare to the community, has not maintained the natural environment and Balinese culture itself (interview 27 January 2021).

Cultural tourism in Bali was recorded to appear so obvious only at the beginning of the issuance of the regional regulations, or after the issuance of Bali Regional Regulation Number 3 of 1974 concerning Cultural Tourism, especially during Ida Bagus Mantra's time as Governor of Bali between 1978 and 1988. Mantra was known as the "Father of Balinese Culture". In supporting cultural tourism, one of Mantra's achievements is the holding of Pesta Kesenian Bali (the Bali Arts Festival) starting in 1979 which was regularly held in the following years except 2020 and 2021 due to the Covid-19 pandemic. After Governor Mantra was replaced by Ida Bagus Oka, Bali Regional Regulation Number 3 of 1991 concerning Cultural Tourism was issued but the flow of globalization was increasingly sweeping the world and had an impact on Bali tourism, especially since the late 1990s and early 2000s. Globalization here is referred to as capitalization. The proof is that a number of tourism facilities establishment have actually seized people's lands and benefited investors (capital owners) and sometimes it becomes the case that is lack of compliance with Tri Hita Karana which is the basis of Bali cultural tourism.

During the era of New Order, especially since the 1990s, tourism in Bali changed from a cultural tourism with a strong grass-root character to a structural one with a grip of capitalism supported by the central power structure (Jakarta) (Aditjondro, 1995; Suasta and Connor, 1999). What takes place is not "tourism for Bali" but on the contrary "Bali for tourism" (Mudana, 1999; Mudana, 2005). Many tourism projects have problems where the space used or will be used has not yet completed the legal process: the feasibility study and the aspects of customary/traditional law. Public problems and protests occurred related to the reclamation of Padanggalak Beach in Denpasar, the reclamation of Serangan Island, plans for the Selasih golf course in Gianyar, Bali Nirwana Resorts in the sacred area of Tanah Lot Temple in Tabanan, Garuda Wisnu Kencana which is now a monument of modern attraction, and so on (Supartha, 1998; Bagus, 1999 and 2004; Mudana, 2005). Even in the reformation era, which is an era towards Indonesia's democratic transition, the case of (planning) the reclamation of Benoa Bay, in which the ecological system of the Benoa Bay sacred area with dozens of small temples (Hindu religious shrines) has high potential to be damaged and abrasion could occur in the area if the reclamation is carried out. In fact, this reclamation plan has political power in the form of Perpres (Presidential Regulation) No. 51/2014 (during the reign of President Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono), which until the second term of President Joko Widodo administration has not been revoked.

From the cases described above, capital owners and tourism investors who cooperate with the government beat civil society instead of a fair and mutually beneficial three-pillar cooperation as conceived in the threefolding stakeholder (Perlas, 2000). Bali experiences what is called tourism, which is later Bali becomes a tourism product (Picard, 1996) or cultural commodification according to Surbakti (2008). This means that many do not understand the cultural philosophy of Balinese land even among the Balinese themselves. Apart from being economic capital, land for the Balinese is a social and cultural-religious space. According to Bagus

(1996), land in Bali includes functions that are related between one another, namely (1) relating to religion, (2) as a human settlement, village, banjar, (3) related to kinship / family, and (4) become a source of livelihood.

Government officials in Bali are more familiar and fluent with the various global tourism model that have emerged expressed in speeches to dominate the Bali cultural tourism discourses. Even during the Reformation era, cultural tourism did not resonate strongly in Bali. Even the issuance of the last Perda, namely Bali Regional Regulation Number 2 of 2012 concerning Bali Cultural Tourism can be said to be a mere legal formality (regulation). Rather than cultural tourism, Governor I Made Mangku Pastika who ruled in the 2008-2013 and 2013-2018 periods prefers to declare the Bali Clean and Green Program at the World Environment Meeting in Nusa Dua on February 20, 2010 and socialized throughout Bali a year later. This program aims to make Bali the Organic Island or the greenest island in Indonesia.

Scientists are also more interested in the tourism discourse which in terms of concept comes from foreign (not Bali), such as ecotourism (Dalem, 2012), sustainable tourism (Pickel-Chevalier and Budarma, 2016), community-based tourism (Ernawati, 2018a and 2018b), including a more localized (Indonesian) discourse such as village tourism (Aryana, 2019). On the other hand, Balinese people even generally understand cultural tourism as simply "art and culture tourism" or more accurately "art tourism"; with the prominent role of art and culture in Bali cultural tourism activities (Mudana, 1999) as represented by the Kecak Dance entity as an icon of Bali cultural tourism in terms of performing arts.

In fact, all discourses regarding Bali tourism have to be related to cultural tourism because Bali cultural tourism has a broad understanding and scope. Lack of understanding of the substance of cultural tourism causes myopic; for example, it has never been explained that ecological, economic and social sustainability in sustainable tourism (which is part of sustainable development) can be related to Tri Hita Karana. Ecological sustainability associated with 'palemahan' (nature); economic sustainability with 'palemahan' and 'pawongan' (human); social sustainability with 'pawongan' and 'parhyangan' (God - spirit). Featuring the uniqueness of Bali(culture), wherein, 'parhyangan' or the harmonious relationship between humans and God in Tri Hita Karana; Bali cultural tourism certainly does not have a precise equivalent in 'sustainable tourism' which is based on rational Western way of thinking. *Parhyangan* can only be associated in general as part of social sustainability. In addition, it is almost not realized that the problems of green and sustainable systems in Bali are known as the 'palemahan' mechanism in the Tri Hita Karana concept which regulates the relationship between humans and the natural surroundings. It is undeniable that for a long time the Balinese Hindu community has been known as a very ecological (environmentally friendly) community with life practices that really protect nature and the realization of sacred ceremonies and worship for the preservation of nature and the world of agriculture expressing gratitude to the Creator (these for example the various traditionalceremonies called 'tumpek uduh/bubuh/wariga/pengatag').

Since the birth of the first Perda on Bali cultural tourism, the authority or the competent institutions in Bali have not been able to formulate the concept of cultural tourism in general as a guideline for the implementation of Bali cultural tourism in the related Perda. A systematic geo-cultural tourism mapping model has not been formulated that born from the implementation of Bali cultural tourism that has been occurring for more than four decades. Without geo-cultural tourism mapping, especially regarding the specification of the products that will be or can be developed by tourism businesses and enjoyed by the tourists; tourism stakeholder does not obtain a clear guidance or substantial understanding of cultural assets as tourism capital that can be explored, developed and experienced.

In this case, Bali geo-cultural tourism mapping, partially or not exhaustively, can refer to the Bali geo-cultural concept, where the geo-culture is none other than 'padma bhuwana' in the idealism of the skalanskala life (physics and non-physis of life) of the Bali Hindu community. 'Padma' means lotus (in Bali it is more often called 'tunjung') and 'bhuwana' is the world or universe. According to Sukawati (2019: 33-37), 'padma bhuwana' is a cultural-based Balinese development approach representing 9 directions which governed by 'Dewa Nawa Sangha', namely the 9 Gods who control the nine directions, namely eight directions plus one in the middle with their respective omnipotence. Sukawati (2019: 11) emphasizes that based on 'padma bhuwana' every Balinese space is basically sacred. Modified from 'padma bhuwana' concept, geo-cultural tourism is conceptualized in this article (Figure 1), which provides an overview of the themes and nuances of cultural tourism that can be experience and enjoyed in the 4 corners and the central part of the island of Bali.

Figure 1: Model of Bali Geo-Cultural Tourism Map

The adaptation of *padma bhuwana* spirituality ideals into Bali geo-cultural tourism simply refers to four main directions, namely north, east, south, and west, plus the middle direction so that in all there are five major centers. Bali geo-cultural tourism mapping is developed based on the characteristic of the nature in each geographical area: the northern region of Bali (Buleleng Regency and parts of Bangli Regency) is suitable for the development of natural and mountainous tourism. The eastern region of Bali (Karangasem Regency and Klungkung Regency) is a place of spiritual tourism development because the east (especially the northeast) is a sacred direction for the Balinese Hindu community. The southern region of Bali (Badung Regency and Denpasar City) with its beautiful beaches is relevant for developing massive coastal tourism and has a 3-S tendency (sea, sand, sun). The western region of Bali (Jembrana Regency and Tabanan Regency) is suitable for developing wildlife tourism and agro-tourism. The central region of Bali (Gianyar Regency and parts of Bangli Regency) is relevant to developing cultural tourism in the sense of art-culture tourism or arts tourism, both performing arts and fine arts (Figure 1).

The proposed Balinese cultural geo-tourism model (Figure 1) is interesting to develop in relation to Bali cultural tourism because all types of tourism mentioned are related to Tri Hita Karana (spiritual aspects of

parhyangan, socio-individual aspects of *pawongan*, and natural aspects of *palemahan*). Physically-geographically, Bali is supported by landscapes and mountains in the north, temples (holy places) in the east, beaches in the south, forests and agriculture in the west, and a variety of arts and culture in the middle. On the other hand, the model with the big five centers is general and not rigid because each destination is still possible to offer other products as alternatives even though they are secondary products in that location. The arrows pointing at each other in the picture show how the inter-aspects of tourism (north, east, south, west, and central Bali) are interconnected, where Bali is a physical, geographic and socio-cultural area that is scalable and abstract which must be managed as one. cultural tourism management.

As a destination that upholds the cultural tourism paradigm, all tourist destinations in Bali should highlight Balinese culture itself. Presently, the results of observations and interviews show that a number of the most important tourist spots such as Sanur, Kuta, Legian, Seminyak, Sanur, Candidasa, Lovina, and even almost all coastal resorts are more impressive with their 3'S (sea, sand, sun) and more suited to be classified as mass tourism by the number of guests who come. These places display very few symbols and markers of Balinese culture both in the context of space and physical objects (artefacts) and social activities and behavior within the scheme of tourism production and consumption (sociofacts), as well as ethics and service values from the host and social interactions of travelers (ideofacts). Karangasem Regency is only able to conceptualize but not yet able to realize the "Karangasem spirit of Bali".

The government under the Governor I Wayan Koster (since 2018) is conceptually good at managing Balinese culture in the vision of his government, namely "Nangun Sad Kerthi Loka Bali". "Sad" means six, "kerthi" (or "kertih") means positive work or activity), and "loka Bali" means Balinese nature (region). Overall *sad kerthi loka* Bali means maintaining the sanctity and harmony of Balinese nature (in this case the six natural sources) and their contents to create: 'kehidupan krama di gumi Bali yang bahagia dan sejahtera lahir dan batin' (a community life in Bali region that is happy and prosperous physically and mentally). This *sad kerthi* consists of (1) *atma kerthi* (spirit), (2) *danu kerthi* (water source), (3) *wana kerthi* (forests including mountains), (4) *segara kerthi* (sea), (5) *jana kerthi* (individual human), and (6) *jagatkerthi* (social relations) (Wiana, 1999: 48). However, in reality this vision has not showed its vitality on Bali cultural tourism, whilst Sad Kerthi Loka Bali and Tri Hita Karana in cultural tourism have not been connected, even though Tri Hita Karana originates from the Sad Kerthi itself. Especially since the beginning of 2020 Bali has been hit by the impact of a global pandemic, namely Covid-19, which has made the focus of the government change significantly and has not been able to carry out its vision and mission to its full potential.

Bali tourism stakeholders as the party operating the regional regulation in the field do not understand the essence of Bali cultural tourism and the knowledge contained therein. The tourism industry can only appreciate the steps in determining cultural tourism, but actually do not know the blue print and how to run it. In the Webinar Road Map to Bali's Next New Normal # 7 held by the Bali Tourism Board and the Association of Indonesian Tourism Industry (GIPI) Bali Friday, July 10, 2020, the Minister of Tourism and Culture (2000-2004) from Bali I Gde Ardika firmly stated that the development of tourism in Bali is a compulsory (absolutely) based on Balinese culture inspired by Hinduism and the Tri Hita Karana foundation, but he himself was very unsure that all tourism sector and business actors in Bali have ever read the Perda.

Conducting analysis of a number of documents and observations of the facts above discovered that Bali cultural tourism has been carried out with poor management. At least the classic POAC (planning, organizing, actuating, controlling) management steps from George R Terry (1956) which were actually relatively general and simple were not properly implemented. Planning for cultural tourism in Bali seems without a clear direction for its implementation. There are many deficiencies in its management and implementation and almost no controlling. It is not clear who (which party) does what in its execution, although, the parties responsible for implementing it is clear in every regulation issued. In Perda No.12 of 2012 Chapter XIII of Guidance and Supervision of Article 32, paragraph (1) states: The Governor shall guide and supervise the activities of Bali cultural tourism.

The lack of good performance in the development of cultural tourism both in the context of cultural spirituality-religiosity, socio-human relations, and physical environmental conditions shows that Tri Hita Karana is not applied in measuring the success or failure of tourism. It is not really used as a parameter whether the tourism entity implementing cultural tourism or not. With such management, it is unclear as to whether the concept of implementing any tourism ventures are in accordance with the promises of the existing regional regulations; how the governmental structures are supposed to oversee Bali cultural tourism development; what are the duties and responsibilities of stakeholders especially the government (executive and legislative), the tourism industry, and society; and what are implementation form and its guidelines; and what are the sanctions

if the regulation is ignored. As a continuation, there will be a question about how the planning, organizing, actuating and controlling are. Bali Province Regional Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Strengthening and Advancement of Balinese Culture; Bali Regional Regulation Number 5 of 2020 concerning Bali Cultural Tourism Implementation Standards; and Bali Governor Regulation No. 28/2020 concerning Bali Tourism Governance do not have the power to support Bali cultural tourism because its implementation is vague and without adequate law enforcement. As a product produced by the government (executive and legislative), the political superstructure, namely the government, is supposed to organize the management of the implementation of cultural tourism. Moreover, in a developing country like Indonesia, the government should have a more role than other institutions or organizations. For this reason, a stakeholder approach is proposed to implement and develop Bali cultural tourism (Figure 2).

Figure 2 shows how Bali cultural tourism cannot be separated from the existence of Tri Hita Karana (God, nature, man) in accordance with the current regional regulations, wherein the implementation of Tri Hita Karana in cultural tourism can also be used as a measuring tool for the success or failure of the implementation of cultural tourism itself. Based on the results of this study, to be successful, the implementation of Bali cultural tourism must prioritize planning, organizing, implementing, and monitoring in a professional and consistent manner which will be carried out by the four pillars in the tetra helix, namely academics, business (tourism industry), society, and government which is abbreviated to ABCG.

Figure 2: Bali Cultural Tourism Development Model - A stakeholder approach

Together with the regional DPR (the house of representative at provincial and regency/city levels), the executives (governor, mayor, and all staffs) should be able to better guard the implementation of Bali cultural tourism. The government, namely political power in the three-holding concept of Perlas (2000) or government in the concept of the tetra helix, at this time (during the leadership of Governor Koster) at least has three very important legal instruments related to the implementation of tourism in general and cultural tourism in particular. The three instruments include: (1) Bali Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Strengthening and Advancement of Balinese Culture, (2) Bali Regional Regulation Number 5 of 2020 concerning Bali Cultural Tourism Implementation Standards, and (3) Bali Governor Regulation Number 28 of 2020 concerning Governance Bali tourism. In addition, the current vision of the Bali government is closely related to the Tri Hita Karana which is the foundation of Bali cultural tourism, namely Nangun Kerthi Loka Bali.

Because Tri Hita Karana lately almost has not been used as a guideline in implementing Bali cultural tourism, practices related to religiosity, humanity, and physical nature (environment) related to tourism do not achieve maximum results. In the context of *parhyangan*, tourist visits often insult local worship place, such as kissing or sitting on the '*pelinggih*' (shrine). In the context of *pawongan*, tourists often become victims of fraud and crime and recently few tourists have become criminals. In the context of *palemahan*, the physical

boundaries of environmental carrying capacity are not well maintained and the physical environment around tourism development is damaged. Groundwater quality has decreased due to uncontrolled development of tourism facilities. Plastic trash scattered about.

Not only environmental destruction, land conversion in Bali has occurred massively, especially since the 1990s. The conversion of land functions from agricultural lands to non-agricultural, including to tourism facilities, amounted to an additional of hundreds of hectares per year. Head of the Bali Province Agriculture and Food Security Service Ida Bagus Wisnuardhana said this is around 700 hectares per year (Wijaya, 2020). Land conversion which is carried out on a large scale for the purpose of tourism will have a negative impact on the physical environment of Bali, especially since there is a land conversion that violates the regional spatial plan. Article 5 of Perda No. 3 of 1991 states, "The development of tourist objects and attractions shall be carried out by taking into account: Cultural preservation and environmental quality" (Paragraph c). Article 5 of Perda No. 2 of 2012 states, "The development of Bali cultural tourism is carried out based on the Regional Spatial Plan (RTRW) of the Province of Bali. If land conversion occurs continuously, it is difficult to imagine how Balinese people maintain their culture and how to maintain cultural tourism.

In the economic aspect, cultural tourism in Bali also does not run ideally. In this case, small investors, such as Tourism SMEs, naturally lose. There is not much tourism-preneurship from grassroot that is able to operate. This is mostly due to the existence of capital-intensive ventures such as in Nusa Dua area that is managed by BTDC (Bali Tourism Development Corporation) which is now ITDC (Indonesia Tourism Development Corporation). In this exclusive area, all hotels are 4 or 5 star and are hotel chains. There was a lot of leakage because almost all of the top leaders of these hotels are not locals and many were not even Balinese. The majority of locals only have low operating positions in the hotel. deVos (1995: 116-146) calls this kind of situation passionate capitalism and not compassionate capitalism or capitalism with social concerns. Mudana (1999) referred them as a "crocodile tourism" ("Bali for tourism") as opposed to cultural tourism ("tourism for Bali"). Principles and Objectives (Chapter II) of Perda No.2 of 2012 states, "The implementation of Bali cultural tourism is carried out based on the principles of benefit, kinship, independence, balance, sustainability, participatory, sustainable, fair and equitable, democratic, equality and unity which is imbued with values; values of Hinduism by applying the Tri Hita Karana philosophy "(Article 2).

Even though tourism as a business is growing rapidly in Bali, socio-economic imbalances in society still occur. The most striking difference is between south Bali, where tourism development has been very intense for a long time, and northern Bali, which is just starting to be developed. The paradox also occurs, because Badung Regency is the most industrialized in tourism and has the highest PAD (local revenue), apparently still has groups of the poor (Patera, 2016). Poverty is also found in people's lives in the tourist area of Ubud, Gianyar, which has a long history of cultural tourism (Sudipa, 2014a; Sudipa, 2014b). In less touristical districts in Bali, poverty is increasing in number. Data from Badan Pusat Statistics of Bali Province (2020) shows, until March 2020, the number of poor people reached 165.19 thousand or 3.78% of the entire population of Bali, wherein March 2020 was the first month of the year in which the Covid-19 pandemic was just started, which later really affects Bali tourism as a whole. As a result of this Corona storm, Badan Pusat Statistik (Radar Bali/Jawa Pos Group, Thursday, February 18, 2021) noted, the new poverty rate in Bali was around 31.73 thousand, an increase compared to the number of poor people in March 2020, which was 165.19 thousand.

CONCLUSION

The lack of legitimate implementation of Bali cultural tourism in general is an evidence of the failure of the political superstructure, namely the government in Bali especially in between transition in communicating the importance of Bali cultural tourism in order to maintain both the tourism business and Balinese culture. Government control in the industrialization of cultural tourism in Bali is also not strong enough to ensure a sound implementation process, in which was reasonably rewarding economically but poorly performed on socio cultural aspects. The promise of harmony between the tourism-economy and culture stated in the Regional Regulation concerning Cultural Tourism ("so that a dynamic reciprocal relationship between tourism and culture can be created which makes them develop synergistically, harmoniously and sustainably in order to provide prosperity to the community, cultural and environmental preservation") does not happening in reality.

In the period of Governor I Wayan Koster, three very good regulations related to the implementation of Bali cultural tourism have been issued. They are (1) Bali Governor Regulation Number 28 of 2020 concerning Bali Tourism Governance (Peraturan Gubernur Bali Nomor 28 Tahun 2020 tentang Tata Kelola

Pariwisata Bali), (2) Bali Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2020 concerning Strengthening and Advancement of Balinese Culture (Peraturan Daerah Bali Nomor 4 Tahun 2020 tentang Penguatan dan Pemajuan Kebudayaan Bali), and (3) Regional Regulation of the Province of Bali Number 5 of 2020 concerning the Implementation Standards of Bali cultural tourism (Peraturan Daerah Bali Nomor 5 Tahun 2020 tentang Standar Penyelenggaraan Kepariwisata Budaya Bali). All of these regulations are theoretically ideal at supporting Bali cultural tourism activities because they directly concern the way how to manage tourism in Bali as good as possible but in fact the implementation of the regulations do not run optimally. This is because the management and the implementation of these regulations are not going well, and currently Bali government since early 2020 has been focused on handling the Covid-19 pandemic which has a very severe impact on Bali tourism economy.

Of the three regulations mentioned above, the last two are very clear about the issue of Bali cultural tourism which can be seen from the titles of the regulations that used the word “budaya (culture)”. Bali Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2020 concerning Strengthening and Advancement of Balinese Culture states that strengthening and advancing Balinese culture is an anticipation of the dynamics of changes in society that are local, national and global which have an impact on the existence of Balinese culture and its development, as well as strengthening national culture and returning Bali as the centre of world civilization/Bali *padma bhuwana*. Regional Regulation of the Province of Bali Number 5 of 2020 concerning the Implementation Standards of Bali cultural tourism, in Article 13, it is stated that the Bali cultural tourism Standard is the setting of benchmarks which are used as guidelines and the basis for evaluating the implementation of Bali cultural tourism; and Article 14, the Implementation of Bali cultural tourism is a series of tourism activities based on local wisdom, including among others products, services and/or management. Even in the last regulation (No 5 of 2020) it is clearly stated that Bali cultural tourism is Bali tourism based on Balinese culture which is inspired by the Tri Hita Karana philosophy which is derived from Sad Kerthi's cultural values and local wisdom and is based on Balinese taksu (Article 12) in which in general *taksu* is a spiritual power that is believed to make something or someone gain more power than something or someone who does not have it. This regulation seems to be trying to increase the strength of the Bali cultural tourism position but its implementation is not optimal so that it does not have a meaning and impact.

Overcoming the problems described above, what really needs to be done is the re-management in the implementation of Bali cultural tourism through the consolidation of the three pillars in implementing cultural tourism, namely all levels of government in Bali (that is province, regency, district, and village/*kelurahan*), components of the tourism industry, and Balinese people. In the aspects of planning, organizing, actuating, and controlling according to modern management (Terry, 1956) all those three components as described in Perlas (2000)'s threefolding concept would be far more perfect if it was added by academics to become the tetra helix of Bali cultural tourism. The involvement of academics both as related scientific experts and as critical intellectuals is very important in criticizing the implementation of Bali cultural tourism itself. This study proposes that the model of geo-Bali cultural tourism in Figure 1 can be implemented according to the working mechanism of the Bali cultural tourism development model with the stakeholder approach in Figure 2.

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